

Simple syntheses of (*Z*)-7-dodecen-1-ol, (*Z*)-7-tetradecen-1-yl acetate, (*Z*)-9-tetradecenal and (*Z*)-9-hexadecen-1-yl acetate from aleuritic acid

R. N. Majee

Lac Processing and Product Development Division, Indian Institute of Natural Resins and Gums, Namkum, Ranchi-834 010, Jharkhand, India

E-mail : r.n.majee@gmail.com

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Abstract : Insect sex pheromones are used for monitoring and management of crop pests. Four compounds (*Z*)-7-dodecen-1-ol, (*Z*)-7-tetradecen-1-yl acetate, (*Z*)-9-tetradecenal and (*Z*)-9-hexadecen-1-yl acetate reported as components of some important agricultural insect pests have been synthesized from *threo*-aleuritic acid (9,10,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic acid) involving simplified Wittig reactions with improved yield.

Keywords : Sex pheromone, *threo*-aleuritic acid, (*Z*)-7-dodecen-1-ol, (*Z*)-7-tetradecen-1-yl acetate, (*Z*)-9-tetradecenal, (*Z*)-9-hexadecen-1-yl acetate, Wittig reaction.

Introduction

There had been tremendous interest, during the recent years in the use of pheromones in insect pest management programme. This is due to concern about environmental pollution and problems of pest resistance to insecticides.

Sex pheromones can effectively be used for monitoring the lepidopteran pests and their control through mass trapping and mate disruption¹. The sex pheromones of a large number of insect species have been analysed, but those of agricultural pests received more attention².

(*Z*)-7-Dodecen-1-ol frequently occurs in the pheromone blend of moth and butterflies³ while (*Z*)-7-tetradecen-1-yl acetate, (*Z*)-9-tetradecen-1-ol and its acetate have been found to occur in the sex pheromones of a few lepidopterous pests^{4,5}.

Vig *et al.*⁶ reported the synthesis of (*Z*)-7-tetradecen-1-yl acetate (**5**) from non-2-yl-1-ol. Several synthesis of (*Z*)-9-tetradecen-1-ol have been reported in the literature starting from various compounds^{7,8}. Subramanian and Malathi⁹ reported the synthesis of (*Z*)-9-hexadecen-1-yl acetate from *threo*-aleuritic acid involving a multiple step reaction sequence. Majee and Ramani¹⁰ also reported the synthesis of same from *threo*-aleuritic acid in low yield. (*Z*)-9-Tetradecenal (**10**) has been found to occur in the

sex pheromones of few lepidopterous pests¹¹.

The sex pheromones of certain noctuid moths contain (*Z*)-9-hexadecen-1-ol and its acetate as their components. Both the compounds are present in the sex pheromone of *Heliothis subflexa* (Gn)¹² while the latter is present in those of *Mamestra brassiae*¹³ and *Naranga aenescens* M¹⁴ (rice green caterpillar).

Chattopadhyay *et al.*¹⁵ reported the synthesis of (*Z*)-9-hexadecen-1-yl acetate from *threo*-aleuritic acid which involved the conversion of *E* to *Z* configuration through acetylenic route. Majee and Ramani¹⁶ reported the synthesis of the same from *erythro*-aleuritic acid obtained from *threo*-aleuritic acid involving multistep reaction sequences.

Aleuritic acid (9,10,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic acid), occurring in *threo*-form can easily be obtained by alkaline hydrolysis of shellac¹⁷ which is produced in large quantities in India. A simple synthetic sequence for the compound **3**, **5**, **10** and **13** using aleuritic acid as the starting material is reported here.

threo-Aleuritic acid (**1**) on periodate oxidation¹⁸ yielded 7-hydroxyheptanal (**2**) and 9-oxononanoic acid (**6**) respectively. Compound **2** was subjected to simplified Wittig reaction via a solid/liquid phase transfer process with *n*-pentyltriphenyl phosphonium bromide using anhy. K₂CO₃

Reaction sequences :

in toluene to give (*Z*)-7-dodecen-1-ol (3). While 2 on simplified Wittig reaction with *n*-heptyltriphenyl phosphonium bromide using anhy. K₂CO₃ in toluene furnished (*Z*)-9-tetradecen-1-ol (4). Its treatment with acetic anhydride in pyridine yielded (*Z*)-9-tetradecen-1-yl acetate (5).

9-Oxononanoic acid (6) was converted into its methylester (7) using BF₃.Et₂O in dry methanol. Compound 7 on Wittig olefination with *n*-pentyltriphenyl phosphonium bromide using anhy. K₂CO₃ in toluene as above gave (*Z*)-9-tetradecenoate (8), which was reduced with

LAH/Et₂O to obtain (*Z*)-9-tetradecen-1-ol (9), which on treatment with PCC/CH₂Cl₂ yielded (*Z*)-9-tetradecenal (10).

Similarly when compound 7 was treated with *n*-heptyltriphenylphosphonium bromide/anhy. K₂CO₃ in toluene afforded 11. Its reduction with LAH/Et₂O gave (*Z*)-9-hexadecen-1-ol (12), which was acetylated with acetic anhydride in dry pyridine to obtain (*Z*)-9-hexadecen-1-yl acetate (13).

Experimental

Boiling points reported are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 instrument (90 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard. The compounds were routinely checked for their purity by TLC.

7-Hydroxyheptanal (2) : A solution of potassium periodate (9.0 g) in 1 (*N*) H₂SO₄ (450 ml) at 20 °C was added rapidly to a stirred solution of *threo*-aleuritic acid (12.0 g) in a methanol-water solution (300 ml : 300 ml) at 40 °C. After 10 min the mixture was cooled and the solution was extracted immediately with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with brine water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of solvent yielded 7-hydroxyheptanal as a liquid (4.7 g), which was purified through a column of neutral alumina by eluting with ether; v_{max} : 3410 (-OH), 1725 (-CHO) cm⁻¹ (Found : C, 64.7; H, 10.7. Calcd. for C₇H₁₄O₂ : C, 64.6; H, 10.7%); ¹H NMR : 2.45 (2H, m, CH₂CHO), 2.40 (1H, br, CH₂OH, D₂O exchangeable), 3.72 (2H, t, CH₂OH), 9.91 (1H, t, CH₂CHO).

(Z)-7-Dodecen-1-ol (3) : A mixture of *n*-pentyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (4.3 g), 7-hydroxyheptanal (2.1 g), anhy. K₂CO₃ (1.5 g) and toluene (35 ml) was refluxed with stirring for 4 h. The mixture was then filtered and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue obtained was recuperated with ether to precipitate the remaining triphenyloxide, if any. The ethereal solution was filtered, evaporated and the resultant residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina with ether as eluent to afford pure product as a liquid (1.9 g);

v_{max} : 3425 (-OH), 725 (CH $\stackrel{(Z)}{=}$ CH) cm⁻¹ (Found : C, 78.1; H, 12.9. C₁₂H₂₄O requires : C, 78.2; H, 13.0%).

(*Z*)-7-Tetradecen-1-ol (**4**): A mixture of **2** (3.7 g), *n*-heptyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (7.6 g), anhy. K_2CO_3 (2.8 g) in toluene (50 ml) was refluxed with stirring for 4 h and processed as above to yield **4** as a liquid (3.3 g), which was purified chromatographically over neutral alumina using ether as eluent; ν_{max} : 3424(-OH),

^(Z)
728 (CH = CH) cm^{-1} (Found: C, 79.1; H, 13.1. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{28}O$: C, 79.2; H, 13.2%); 1H NMR: 0.9 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.31 (16H, m, saturated CH_2), 2.07 (4H, m, allylic protons), 3.6 (2H, t, CH_2OH), 5.48–5.60 (2H, m, CH=CH).

(*Z*)-7-Tetradecen-1-yl acetate (**5**): Compound **4** (2.0 g) was stirred with dry pyridine (20 ml) and Ac_2O (20 ml) for 24 h and its usual work-up with ether afforded **5** as a liquid, which was purified over a column of neutral alumina (yield 1.7 g); ν_{max} : 1740 (- $COOCH_3$), 730

^(Z)
(-CH = CH) cm^{-1} (Found: C, 75.5; H, 11.8. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{30}O_2$: C, 75.6; H, 11.8%); 1H NMR: 0.93 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.35 (16H, m, CH_2), 1.9 (4H, br, $CH_2-CH=CH-CH_2$), 2.1 (3H, s, -O-CO- CH_3), 2.15 (4H, m, allylic methylenes), 3.95 (2H, t, $-CH_2-O-Ac$), 5.42–5.65 (2H, m, CH=CH).

9-Oxononanoic acid (**6**): *threo*-Aleuritic acid (1, 10.0 g) on periodate oxidation following the reported procedure¹⁸ yielded titled compound (6.2 g) as a viscous oil, purified by column chromatography; ν_{max} : 1725 (-CHO), 1700 (-COOH) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR: 1.1–1.8 (10H, m, $-CH_2COOH$), 2.3 (4H, t, $-CH_2-CHO$), 9.54 (1H, t, -CHO), 9.84 (1H, bs, COOH).

Methyl 9-oxononanoate (**7**): Compound **6** (5.0 g) was esterified with dry methanol containing $BF_3 \cdot Et_2O$ to give **7** (4.7 g) as a liquid, b.p. 90–95 °C/0.2 mm (lit.¹⁸: 86–92 °C/0.2 mm); ν_{max} : 1730 (-CHO), 1740 (- $COOCH_3$) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR: 1.0–1.8 (10H, m, 5- CH_2), 1.92–2.5 (4H, m, CH_2COOCH_3 and CH_2-CHO), 3.62 (3H, s, $-CO_2CH_3$), 8.7 (1H, t, -CHO).

Methyl (*Z*)-9-tetradecenoate (**8**): A mixture of *n*-pentyltriphenyl phosphonium bromide (3.8 g), methyl 9-oxononanoate (1.8 g), anhy. K_2CO_3 (1.4 g) and toluene (30 ml) was refluxed with stirring for 4 h and following the procedure as earlier to afford methyl (*Z*)-9-tetradecenoate as a liquid (1.7 g). The product was purified by column chromatography; ν_{max} : 1740 (- $COOCH_3$),

^(Z)
721 (-CH = CH) cm^{-1} (Found: C, 75.0; H, 11.6. $C_{15}H_{28}O_2$ requires: C, 74.9; H, 11.6%); 1H NMR: 3.66 (3H, s, $COOCH_3$), 5.28 (2H, t, CH=CH).

(*Z*)-9-Tetradecen-1-ol (**9**): Compound **8** (5.0 g) was reduced with LAH (2.2 g) in dry ether (40 ml). After refluxing for 2 h, the mixture was cooled and excess of LAH was destroyed with dilute HCl. Its usual work up with ether gave crude alcohol (3.2 g) as a liquid, which was purified by distillation, b.p. 122–125 °C/0.08 mm (lit.⁸ 122–125 °C/0.08 mm); ν_{max} : 3350 (-OH), 3000,

^(Z)
1640, 1050, 720 (-CH = CH) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR: 0.9 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.1–1.5 (16H, m, $(CH_2)_n$), 1.96 (4H, bs, $(CH_2)_n$), 2.1 (1H, s, -OH), 3.56 (2H, t, OCH_2), 5.16 (2H, m, HC=CH).

(*Z*)-9-Tetradecenal (**10**): To a well stirred solution of PCC (2.2 g) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (20 ml), the above alcohol (1.6 g) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (20 ml) was added in one lot. After stirring for 4 h TLC indicated the absence of alcohol. The reaction mixture was diluted with anhy. ether and the supernatant decanted from the gummy mass. The ethereal extract was passed through a column of neutral alumina to get rid of impurities and the solvent evaporated off to obtain the titled compound (1.3 g); ν_{max} : 1735

^(Z)
(-CHO), 705 (-CH = CH) cm^{-1} (Found: C, 79.8; H, 12.2. $C_{14}H_{26}O$ requires: C, 80.0; H, 12.3%).

Methyl (*Z*)-9-hexadecenoate (**11**): A mixture of *n*-heptyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (3.8 g), methyl 9-oxononanoate (1.9 g), anhy. K_2CO_3 (1.4 g) and toluene (30 ml) was refluxed while stirring for 4 h. The mixture was then filtered and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue obtained was recuperated with ether to precipitate the remaining triphenyloxide, if any. The ethereal solution was filtered, evaporated to give titled compound as a liquid (1.7 g), which was purified by column chromatography; ν_{max} : 1735 (C=O of ester

^(Z)
carbonyl), 725 (CH = CH) cm^{-1} (Found: C, 76.0; H, 11.8. $C_{17}H_{32}O_2$ requires: C, 76.1; H, 11.9%).

(*Z*)-9-Hexadecen-1-ol (**12**): The above ester **11** (3.0 g) in anhy. ether (15 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred suspension of LAH (0.8 g) in anhy. ether (40 ml) and

refluxed for 2 h, its usual work-up with ether afforded alcohol **12** as a liquid, which was purified by distillation (2.3 g), b.p. 128–132 °C/0.5 mm; v_{\max} : 3400 (-OH),

(Z)
725 (-CH = CH) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$: 0.94 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.3 (20H, s, $(\text{CH}_2)_{10}$), 1.91–2.2 (4H, m, allylic protons), 3.62 (2H, t, CH_2OH), 5.36 (2H, m, olefinic protons).

(Z)-9-Hexadecen-1-yl acetate (**13**) : The foregoing alcohol (2.0 g) was stirred with dry pyridine (2.8 ml) and acetic anhydride (5.6 ml) for 24 h at room temperature. Usual work-up with ether afforded **13** as a liquid (1.4 g), which was purified by column chromatography; v_{\max} :

(Z)
1740 ($-\text{COCH}_3$), 730 (-CH = CH) cm^{-1} (Found : C, 76.6; H, 12.0. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$: C, 76.5; H, 12.1%); $^1\text{H NMR}$: 0.93 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.31 (20H, s, $-(\text{CH}_2)_{10}$), 2.1 (7H, m, allylic protons), 4.06 (2H, t, CH_2COCH_3), 5.40 (2H, m, $\text{CH}=\text{CH}$).

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